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Research on the development prospects and cultivation countermeasures of English majors in cross-border E-commerce backgrounds

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Abstract

Abstract: In recent years, the development of e-commerce has been very rapid no matter in which country or region. Based on its broad development prospects, a large number of investors have invested in the field, which also makes the competition between e-commerce increasingly fierce. As an emerging mode of e-commerce, live broadcasting, relying on the development of Internet technology, has become an important way of e-commerce with goods. However, China's e-commerce market has become mature, with high competitive pressure and reduced opportunities in the industry. In order to make better use of the English majors' own advantages, so as to broaden their development prospects in this industry, this paper starts from this background, analyzes the current situation and development prospects of cross-border e-commerce, studies the requirements and expectations of this industry for English majors, and puts forward the cultivation and practice programs for English majors in this direction.

Keywords: Cross-Border E-Commerce; Live Streaming with Goods; English Major; Employment Prospect; Talent Cultivation

1. Introduction

The history of e-commerce can be traced back to the early 1990s, when doing business over the Internet was still a fairly rare thing. It wasn't until 1995 that Amazon, the famous online bookstore, opened its website and began selling books and other products. At that time, e-commerce was mainly B2C (business-to-consumer) because most people did not have the awareness of shopping online at that time. After 2000, with the continuous development of Internet technology, e-commerce began to enter a period of rapid development, and more new e-commerce platforms appeared, such as Taobao, Jingdong, etc. At the same time, mobile devices and smartphones were also being used for e-commerce. At the same time, the popularity of mobile devices and smartphones has made mobile online shopping an emerging trend.

In 1999, Alibaba was founded, kicking off the development of cross-border e-commerce in China. Since then, with the vigorous development of the "Internet +" new industry, cross-border e-commerce, as an emerging business form and market means, has played an increasingly important role in China's economic development. Talent is one of the most important driving forces to support the development of China's cross-border e-commerce, according to preliminary estimates, only in 2016, the cross-border e-commerce talent gap reached a huge 1.5 million, and in 2017 at a rate of 39% in the increase in the gap continues to increase, according to the "cross-border e-commerce industry in 2017 talent management research and analysis report", the next three years of China's cross-border e-commerce talent gap will be as high as 4.5 million, the talent gap The talent gap is not only reflected in the quantity, but also in the quality. At present, there is still no perfect solution for cross-border e-commerce talent training, and most colleges and universities are still difficult to provide talents directly oriented to the needs of cross-border e-commerce enterprises, and there is a large gap between the market demand and the current situation of talents [1]. In 2023, China's cross-border e-commerce

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import and export amounted to 2.38 trillion yuan, with a growth of 15.6%. At present, cross-border e-commerce has become an important kinetic energy to promote the growth of foreign trade, and all over the world continue to deepen the comprehensive reform of cross-border e-commerce, innovative initiatives, open up the blockages, and promote the accelerated development of cross-border e-commerce business [2].

1.1. Cross-border e-commerce and the current situation of talent demand

1.1.1. Status of cross-border e-commerce

In recent years, with the rapid development of network technology and the transformation of consumers' shopping habits, the domestic e-commerce market scale has shown a rapid growth trend, and the market scale is growing rapidly. Various types of e-commerce platforms have sprung up, covering a wide range of fields from comprehensive e-commerce to vertical e-commerce, providing consumers with a wealth of shopping options. Meanwhile, with the popularization of smartphones and the in-depth development of mobile Internet, the user group of e-commerce is also expanding. Not only has the younger generation become the main force of e-commerce consumption, but more and more middle-aged and old-aged groups have also begun to contact and become accustomed to online shopping. The expansion of the user group provides a solid foundation for the continued growth of the e-commerce market. In order to standardize the order of the e-commerce market and protect the rights and interests of consumers, the state level has continuously improved the regulations and policies related to e-commerce. The introduction of these regulations and policies provides a strong guarantee for the healthy development of the e-commerce market, and also provides clear guidelines for e-commerce enterprises to operate in compliance.

Currently, the domestic e-commerce market presents a pattern of coexistence of diverse business models. In addition to the traditional B2C and C2C modes, emerging modes such as social e-commerce, live e-commerce, and content e-commerce have gradually emerged. These emerging modes have met the different needs of consumers through innovative ways and promoted the diversified development of the e-commerce market. With the deep development of globalization, cross-border e-commerce has become an important part of the e-commerce market. Domestic e-commerce enterprises have been expanding their overseas markets, realizing the global layout of commodities through overseas warehouses and bonded zones. Meanwhile, overseas brands have also entered the Chinese market through cross-border e-commerce platforms, providing consumers with more diversified shopping options.

1.1.2. Cross-border e-commerce talent demand status quo

In recent years, the size of the cross-border e-commerce market has continued to expand with remarkable growth. With the acceleration of globalization and the popularization of Internet technology, more and more consumers tend to buy overseas goods through cross-border e-commerce platforms. This trend not only drives the rapid growth of the cross-border e-commerce market, but also promotes the further development of international trade. Currently, the major platforms in the cross-border e-commerce market include internationally recognized e-commerce platforms such as Amazon, eBay, and Sizzler, as well as some regional cross-border e-commerce platforms. These platforms provide consumers with a rich selection of goods and a convenient shopping experience through different business models such as B2B, B2C and C2C. Meanwhile, governments have introduced policies to support the development of cross-border e-commerce. For example, they provide tax incentives, reduce import tariffs, and simplify the registration process of cross-border e-commerce. These policies have created a favorable environment for the development of cross-border e-commerce and also supported the facilitation of international trade. With the development of cross-border e-commerce, consumer behavior has also changed. More and more consumers begin to pay attention to the brand, quality and price of overseas goods, and make comparisons and choices through cross-border e-commerce platforms. In addition, consumers have higher and higher requirements for shopping experience, such as faster delivery and better after-sales service. The development of cross-border e-commerce cannot be separated from the support of technological innovation. The application of artificial intelligence, big data, blockchain and other technologies provides more efficient and safer services for cross-border e-commerce.

1.1.3. E-commerce Live Streaming

With the popularization of mobile Internet and the maturity of live broadcasting technology, e-commerce live broadcasting, as an emerging sales model, has continued to expand its market scale. More and more consumers watch the display of goods, understand the details of products through the live broadcast platform, and complete the purchase behavior during the live broadcast. The sales of live e-commerce show a rapid growth trend, becoming a new growth point in the e-commerce industry. The content of e-commerce live broadcasting covers a variety of fields such as clothing, beauty, home, digital, etc., which meets the diverse shopping needs of consumers. At the same time, the form of live content is also constantly innovating, from the simple display of goods to the development of situational drama, show, and other forms, to enhance the audience's viewing experience and desire to buy. However, the development of

live e-commerce cannot be separated from the synergy of the entire industrial chain. From the supplier to the e-commerce platform, to the logistics company, all links need to work closely together to ensure the smooth progress of live sales. At the same time, with the expansion of the live e-commerce market, enterprises in the upstream and downstream of the industry chain are also emerging, providing strong support for the development of live e-commerce.

In summary, e-commerce live broadcasting, as an emerging sales model, has continued to expand its market size, a youthful consumer group, rich and diverse live content, continuous innovation in technology application, strengthened industry chain synergy, a gradually obvious competition pattern, and increasingly perfect regulations and supervision. In the future, with the progress of technology and the maturity of the market, e-commerce live broadcasting will continue to usher in a broad development space and opportunities. At the same time, it is also necessary for all parties to work together to strengthen cooperation and supervision, and promote the healthy development of the e-commerce live broadcast industry.

1.2. Problems in cross-border e-commerce talent training

1.2.1. College students' passion for cross-border e-commerce startups high, but success rate low

As the domestic e-commerce market has become saturated, the competition among major platforms has become more and more intense. New entrants need to face the pressure of market share being divided up and the increased cost of acquiring user traffic, while established e-commerce platforms are facing the risk of slowing down user growth and declining market share. To cope with this challenge, e-commerce platforms need to continuously improve service quality, optimize user experience, and attract and retain users by increasing investment in marketing and promotion. The normal operation of e-commerce platforms cannot be separated from the support of information technology, but this also brings technical security risks. Network attacks, data leakage, system paralysis and other incidents occur from time to time, bringing huge economic losses and reputation damage to e-commerce platforms. Therefore, e-commerce platforms need to strengthen technical security and invest more resources in technical research and development and security. With the rise of labor, rent and other costs, e-commerce platforms are facing the pressure of rising costs. Because e-commerce platforms source goods from a wide range of sources, supply chain management is more difficult. Issues such as instability of suppliers, uneven quality of goods, and delays in logistics and distribution may bring losses to e-commerce platforms. E-commerce platforms need to establish stable cooperative relationships with suppliers and strengthen commodity quality monitoring and logistics and distribution management to ensure the stability and reliability of the supply chain. If the supply chain is not properly managed, the quality of goods on the e-commerce platform will be uneven, and this will lead to a decline in consumer trust. Consumer trust crisis will not only affect the reputation and image of the e-commerce platform, but also reduce user stickiness and purchase intention. E-commerce platforms need to strengthen the supervision and audit of commodity quality and establish a perfect consumer rights protection mechanism to rebuild consumer trust. Therefore, the government needs to strictly regulate the e-commerce industry and introduce relevant regulations and policies in a timelier manner. E-commerce platforms, on the other hand, need to pay close attention to policy trends and make timely adjustments to their business models and operational strategies to avoid unnecessary risks caused by violations of regulations. At the same time, the policy changes may also bring about industry reshuffle, some do not adapt to the new policy of the e-commerce platform may face the risk of being eliminated.

The seventeenth National Congress of the Communist Party of China explicitly proposed that "policies to support independent entrepreneurship and self-employment should be improved, so that more workers can become entrepreneurs." College students are the most energetic and creative group, containing great creative enthusiasm and entrepreneurial potential. Governments at all levels should put encouraging and guiding college students' entrepreneurship in an important position, actively create a favorable environment, increase policy support and guidance, and build a green channel for college students to start their own businesses. In recent years, cross-border e-commerce has consistently maintained a growth rate of about 30%, and cross-border e-commerce has developed from an economic phenomenon to a business model that is solidifying into a new type of trade. Alibaba, NetEase Kaola Haibao as the representative of the cross-border e-commerce market end of the first practice for the global industry to provide experience, but also for college students to provide new ideas for innovation and entrepreneurship, college students around the e-commerce is also from the online store, micro-businesses, such as shopping on behalf of the transfer of the cross-border e-commerce project, cross-border e-commerce projects have become a fertile ground for innovation and entrepreneurship.

According to the 2016 China College Student Entrepreneurship Report released by Renmin University of China, nearly 90% of China's college students have the intention to start their own business, and 20% have strong entrepreneurial intentions. This phenomenon shows that the entrepreneurial culture has left a deep mark on China's college student population. At the same time, in recent years, China's major universities have been committed to cultivating an

entrepreneurial atmosphere on their campuses, providing entrepreneurial education and training to current college students, guiding them to participate in innovation and entrepreneurship competitions, and actively encouraging them to participate in social practice to accumulate entrepreneurial experience, and so on. It is also mentioned in the report that as the number of graduates increases year by year, the number of college students choosing to start their own business after graduation is also increasing, and more and more college students are realizing entrepreneurship and employment with the help of e-commerce platform which is "low-cost, low-threshold, and quick-return". According to the results of entrepreneurship, the overall trend of entrepreneurship among Chinese college students tends to increase, but the success rate of entrepreneurship is only about 2%, which is far lower than the success rate of general enterprises, and also lower than the success rate of entrepreneurship among college students in Europe and the United States (20%-30%). The main reasons for analyzing this situation are: firstly, the school is vigorously promoting the independent entrepreneurship of college students at the same time, the market for the acceptance of college students' entrepreneurship is still relatively low, do not trust college students' ability to operate and product quality, resulting in college students' enterprises to obtain orders is even more difficult; secondly, college students lack of understanding of the relevant industry policies and regulations, the upstream and downstream competition in the market, and the needs of specific customers. Lack of understanding, many college students' entrepreneurial plans will fall into the embarrassing situation of "closed door"; again, the government now strongly supports entrepreneurship, but most college students know very little about entrepreneurial policies and incentives, most of the start-up capital is raised through internal resources, mainly through personal and family borrowing, which is obviously not effective in meeting the financial needs of entrepreneurship. These obviously cannot effectively meet the financial needs of entrepreneurship, in contrast, the financing of university students' entrepreneurship in foreign countries mainly relies on angel investment. Therefore, it is of great significance to respond to the call of the state to encourage entrepreneurship, build entrepreneurial platforms for college students, and improve the success rate of college students' entrepreneurship, which is also a place where colleges and universities should focus on improving the cultivation of talents.

1.2.2. College students' willingness to do internships is strong, but there are many obstacles to doing so

School-enterprise cooperation, increase students' internship practice opportunities, improve students' hands-on ability and thinking and decision-making ability, from the concept is indisputable, but in practice it is difficult to make substantial progress, the reason is mainly due to the enterprise participation enthusiasm is not high, and even if the participation is often in the form of the students cannot learn substantive things. According to survey data, most students said, although not to graduation, but the employment pressure makes them very sense of urgency, and internships can undoubtedly add a little bit of leverage for the future job search, after all, students with internships than no internships will be much higher than the likelihood of obtaining a stable job opportunities, usually also have a higher salary. Therefore, if you can find an internship, it doesn't matter if you have to pay for transportation and telephone expenses. But even so, nearly 30% of the respondents still think that it is not easy or even difficult to find an internship; half of the respondents think that the internship position is only a little bit related to their majors as well as almost unrelated to their majors. Forty percent of the interns said that they basically took the initiative to look for things to do during their internships; fifty percent of the interns said that they could only wait for their supervisors to make arrangements; and nearly ten percent of the interns said that they had nothing to do without taking the initiative to ask, and that they could only amuse themselves by staying in the office the whole day. In a word, most of the interns, especially the short-term interns of 2-3 months, find it difficult to find internship jobs that match their majors, and it is hard for them to get professional skills upgraded before they work formally. The main reasons for the low motivation of enterprises are: it is difficult for enterprises to bear the business risks brought by students' internship, such as leaking business information, offending potential customers, etc.; internship students fail to meet the required professional ethics and sense of responsibility, and often leave their jobs casually; the school is unable to give the enterprises the corresponding returns. Instead of seeking others, it is better to seek for oneself, have their own long-term and stable internship base to really solve the plight of students' internship difficulties, therefore, it is necessary to build their own professional internship base, and it is also the focus of the reform of talent cultivation.

Cross-border e-commerce involves transnational transportation, so logistics issues become the primary challenge. This includes problems such as high cost and longtime of international transportation, difficulty in tracking goods, and complicated return processing. For e-commerce platforms, it is crucial to establish an efficient and reliable cross-border logistics system. And different countries have different tariff and tax policies, which is also an important issue for cross-border e-commerce. Differences in tax rates for different goods in different countries may lead to price fluctuations and affect consumers' purchasing decisions. E-commerce platforms need to familiarize themselves with the tax policies of each country and reasonably plan their pricing strategies to reduce the impact of taxes on consumers' purchasing intentions. At the same time, cross-border e-commerce needs to face the problem of multi-currency payment and currency conversion. Payment methods, payment habits and payment security standards vary from country to country,

which poses challenges to e-commerce platforms in terms of complicating the payment process and increasing the cost of currency conversion. E-commerce platforms need to provide multiple payment methods and support multiple currency conversions to meet the needs of consumers in different countries. The laws and regulations of different countries have different requirements for cross-border e-commerce. Platforms need to comply with the laws and regulations of each country to ensure that goods are legally compliant and to handle various legal disputes. Differences in data protection and privacy regulations also pose challenges for cross-border e-commerce.

In the international market, competition is fierce and branding has become an important challenge for cross-border e-commerce. E-commerce platforms need to develop unique brand strategies to enhance brand awareness and influence in order to stand out in the competition. At the same time, it also needs to continuously optimize its products and services to meet consumers' needs and enhance brand loyalty. Consumer trust is a key factor in cross-border e-commerce. Consumers are often skeptical about international shopping, worrying about issues such as product quality and after-sales service. E-commerce platforms need to establish a trust mechanism and provide reliable shopping protection and quality after-sales service to win consumers' trust. Different countries have different cultural backgrounds and market habits, which put forward requirements for cross-border e-commerce marketing and product positioning. E-commerce platforms need to understand the culture and consumption habits of their target markets and adjust their product strategies to meet the needs and preferences of local consumers. Under this premise, cross-border e-commerce operators need to communicate with consumers in different countries, and the language barrier has become an important issue. E-commerce platforms need to provide multi-language support to ensure smooth and unobstructed communication with consumers and avoid misunderstandings and disputes caused by language issues.

1.2.3. E-commerce Live Streaming

The core of the live carry is the product, and the quality of the product is directly related to the consumer's buying experience and the anchor's reputation. If there are problems with the quality of the product, it will not only lead to consumer complaints and returns, but also affect the anchor's reputation and fan trust. Therefore, the anchor and team of the live broadcast with goods need to strictly screen and audit the products to ensure that the quality of the goods sold meets the standards. The live broadcast of goods involves the procurement of goods, warehousing, logistics and other links, and requires efficient supply chain management to ensure that the goods are delivered to the hands of consumers in a timely manner. If the supply chain management is not good, it may lead to out-of-stock goods, delayed delivery and other problems, affecting the consumer experience and trust. The business model of live streaming with goods is built on the trust relationship between consumers and anchors. The level of consumer trust will directly affect the effect and conversion rate of carry goods. To establish and maintain consumer trust, anchors need to show a sincere and professional attitude, keep their promises, and provide real and credible product information and buying advice. Live carry anchors need to have good diction, image and professional knowledge, as well as a high degree of responsibility and professional ethics. The anchor's demeanor and attitude will directly affect the consumer's purchase decision and trust. Therefore, anchors need to continuously improve their quality and ability to adapt to the needs of live banding. The ultimate goal of live streaming is to improve user experience and conversion rate. Anchors and merchants need to continuously optimize the live content, interactive methods, product display, etc., in order to improve user experience and satisfaction. At the same time, it is also necessary to pay attention to user feedback and demand, and timely adjust and improve the live broadcast strategy to meet the personalized needs of users.

Technically, live streaming bandwagons require a stable live streaming technology platform to transmit video and audio, as well as to handle user interaction and data statistics. The stability and ease of use of the technology platform is crucial to the effect of live streaming. If you encounter technical problems such as live streaming lag, blurred images, and unsynchronized audio and video, it will not only affect the user experience, but may also reduce the effect of live streaming. At the same time, live streaming with goods needs to comply with relevant laws and regulations, including advertising law, consumer rights protection law, e-commerce law and so on. Anchors and merchants need to ensure that they do not infringe intellectual property rights, spread false advertisements, or engage in unfair competition during the live broadcast. If they violate laws and regulations, they may face fines, blocking or even legal liability. Competition in the field of live streaming with goods is becoming increasingly fierce, and anchors and merchants need to constantly innovate and optimize the content and form of live streaming in order to attract and retain users. This includes offering attractive goods and developing unique marketing strategies.

1.3. Employment prospect

1.3.1. cross-border e-commerce operations

Cross-border e-commerce operations is one of the core positions in the industry. Practitioners need to master key skills such as operation strategy, product management, order processing, and customer service on cross-border e-commerce

platforms. Excellent cross-border e-commerce operators can help companies boost platform traffic and increase user stickiness, thereby realizing sales growth.

1.3.2. Marketing Planning

Marketing planning is an important tool for cross-border e-commerce companies to increase brand awareness and sales. Practitioners need to understand the needs of consumers in the target market, develop marketing strategies that are in line with local culture and consumption habits, and attract potential customers through effective promotional means to increase the conversion rate.

1.3.3. Supply Chain Management

The supply chain management of cross-border e-commerce involves multiple aspects such as commodity procurement, inventory management, logistics and distribution. Practitioners need to ensure the quality and supply stability of goods, while optimizing logistics costs and improving overall operational efficiency. Excellent supply chain managers can help companies maintain an edge in the fierce market competition.

1.3.4. Data analysis and forecasting

In the field of cross-border e-commerce, data analysis and prediction play an increasingly important role. Practitioners need to use data analysis tools and methods to dig deeper into user behavior data, sales data, etc., to provide data support for enterprise decision-making. Through the prediction of market trends, enterprises can better grasp market opportunities and layout in advance.

1.3.5. Overseas Business Expansion

With the continuous development of cross-border e-commerce market, overseas business expansion has become a strategic choice for more and more enterprises. Practitioners need to understand the policies and regulations, cultural differences and consumption habits of overseas markets to provide strong support for enterprises to expand overseas markets. Successful overseas business development can help enterprises open up new market space and achieve wider user coverage.

1.3.6. cross-border e-commerce live

Cross-border e-commerce live streaming, a form of shopping, is legally a commercial advertising activity. Anchors broadcast live on cross-border e-commerce platforms to bring goods. Depending on the specific behavior, the anchor also bears the responsibility of "advertising spokesperson", "advertising publisher" or "advertiser".

1.4. Training program

1.4.1. Cross-border e-commerce operation and marketing planning

First of all, it is necessary to clarify the cultivation objectives and cultivate professionals with knowledge and skills of cross-border e-commerce operation and marketing planning, who are able to master the operation rules, marketing strategies and promotion means of cross-border e-commerce platforms, and have the ability to independently carry out cross-border e-commerce business. Secondly, the curriculum system should be constructed, and according to the cultivation objectives, the curriculum system including cross-border e-commerce overview, cross-border e-commerce platform operation, cross-border e-commerce marketing strategy, cross-border e-commerce logistics management, cross-border e-commerce payment and settlement, cross-border e-commerce laws and regulations should be constructed. At the same time, practical teaching is strengthened to enhance students' practical ability and operational experience and improve their cross-border e-commerce operation level through school-enterprise cooperation and internship training. In the process of cultivation, we focus on cultivating students' comprehensive qualities such as innovative thinking, teamwork and communication ability, and improving their comprehensive ability of cross-border e-commerce operation and market marketing planning [3].

1.4.2. Supply Chain Management

First of all, it is necessary to set clear learning objectives so that students can master the basic theories, design, methods, management, inventory strategy, information strategy, etc. of supply chain management, and be able to manage and solve problems by applying the relevant concepts of supply chain management. It is also necessary to focus on practical teaching, through school-enterprise cooperation, internship training and other ways to strengthen students' practical ability and operational experience, and improve students' supply chain management level. At the same time, we should

strengthen the construction of teaching staff, introduce teachers with practical experience in supply chain management and teaching experience, strengthen the training and learning of teachers, and improve the professional level and teaching quality of teachers. Innovate in education mode, study how to innovate the education mode of supply chain management applied talents training, including the application of new teaching methods and tools such as online learning, practical teaching, virtual simulation, etc., in order to improve the cultivation effect and students' practical ability. Meanwhile, under the background of digital economy, it is more and more important to cultivate students' comprehensive quality of digital intelligence and lifelong learning. Institutions should focus on the cultivation of students' comprehensive quality of digital intelligence in the process of exploring how to carry out the cultivation of supply chain management applied talents, including the use of digital technology to solve problems, the use of intelligent means to enhance the ability of teamwork, etc., and the cultivation of lifelong learning consciousness of students to adapt to the current stage of the fast-changing digital intelligence supply chain environment [4].

1.4.3. Data Predictive Analytics

In this regard, one should first master basic data analysis skills, learn the basics of statistics, data mining, machine learning, and master the basic skills of data cleaning, data visualization, data modeling and so on. It is also important to focus on the accumulation of practical experience, through participation in actual data analysis projects, to understand the application of data predictive analytics in the actual business, and to accumulate practical experience. At the same time, focusing on industry trends and technology development is conducive to understanding the latest news and technology development trends in the field of data predictive analytics, and keeping up with the learning and exploration of new technologies. Finally, focus on innovative thinking and problem solving ability. Data predictive analytics needs to face complex data and business scenarios, and requires innovative thinking and problem solving skills.

1.4.4. Overseas Business Expansion

Firstly, training in language and cultural adaptability and international market knowledge is provided to help employees better integrate into the local market and cultural environment. At the same time, training in international market knowledge and overseas market research skills is conducted in order to improve the business ability and professionalism of employees so that they can better conduct overseas business. It is also possible to improve employees' international market knowledge by inviting industry experts and overseas market researchers to conduct training. Finally, it is necessary to establish effective incentive mechanisms and career development plans to encourage employees to actively participate in overseas business development and provide them with opportunities and space for career development in order to attract and retain outstanding overseas business talents.

1.4.5. Cross-border e-commerce live

First of all, it is necessary to improve the "English + live" cross-border e-commerce course system. The rapid development of cross-border live e-commerce requires more and more cross-border live e-commerce talents to have higher and higher language and comprehensive ability, therefore, the training of cross-border live e-commerce personnel must innovate the reform of the course content and improve the course knowledge system. In terms of curriculum, we can consider opening courses such as "cross-border e-commerce store operation", "visual marketing design" and "overseas promotion". Secondly, the cultivation of cross-border e-commerce live talents needs to organically integrate the content of English + live broadcast into the curriculum, which can be added to the live broadcast module in the "cross-border e-commerce English" course, integrating live broadcasting skills of anchors into English language teaching, and designing daily e-commerce live broadcasts into specific live broadcasting scenarios to improve students' learning interest. Again, in the practical courses, actively introduce the practical projects of enterprises to train students to be familiar with the whole cross-border live e-commerce process from online product consultation to order and payment, from logistics and transportation to after-sale evaluation, and from dispute handling to offline cooperation. Finally, deepen school-enterprise cooperation, build productive training bases together, cultivate students' practical skills and improve their employment quality.

Cross-border e-commerce live personnel need to have good ability to use English to communicate and negotiate with customers. The cultivation and practice of cross-border e-commerce live streaming personnel's ability can be based on the scenario teaching method. For example, in order to improve the learners' English communication skills, simulated situations of listening and speaking in cross-border e-commerce English are created. In addition, in the process of scenario teaching, diversified evaluation mechanisms such as student self-assessment, teacher evaluation, and enterprise tutor evaluation should be established, and the evaluation results should be fed back to the students in a timely manner, so as to facilitate the students' timely adjustment of learning strategies. At the same time, the real enterprise combat projects into the school, the two sides to build a set of "live scene + course teaching + combat projects"

as one of the productive training bases, to create students to carry out cross-border e-commerce live training, internships, combat, entrepreneurship learning platform, for students to accumulate more experience in live broadcasting, laying the foundation for entrepreneurship [5]. What can't be ignored is the live skill training, for the characteristics of live sales, relevant skill training, such as live speech, product introduction, interactive skills, etc., in order to improve the effect and conversion rate of live sales. Understand the rules, processes, trends, etc. of cross-border e-commerce in order to better conduct live sales and promotion. And live sales need to have a good image and temperament, so you need to carry out relevant image and temperament training to improve the attractiveness of the live broadcast and the audience's trust. Finally, by participating in actual live sales projects, we can accumulate practical experience and improve the ability and level of live sales.

2. Conclusion

Under the background of cross-border e-commerce, English major college students are facing unprecedented development opportunities and challenges. With the increasing frequency of global trade and the booming development of e-commerce, cross-border e-commerce has become an important trend, which provides more employment opportunities for English majors, as well as a broad stage and unlimited possibilities, however, it also puts forward higher requirements for English majors. Therefore, in order to cultivate English major college students adapted to the development of cross-border e-commerce, we need to develop a scientific training program. Only in this way can we better meet the social demand for English majors and promote the sustainable development of cross-border e-commerce. At the same time, it can also enhance the cross-border e-commerce business ability of enterprises, help local enterprises better explore the international market, and thus improve the international trade competitiveness of local enterprises. In the long run, this can improve the efficiency and transparency of international trade and is expected to further promote global trade liberalization.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Author Statement

All authors agree with submission of this version.

Availability of data

The datasets used and/or analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

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